

How to Cite (APA): Günesen Akansu, B. & Kapanoğlu, M. (2025). Scheduling under uncertainty for industry 4.0 applications: a simulation-based genetic algorithm approach. In Proceedings of the IMSS'25 (pp. 309–321). Düzce University - Türkiye, 25–27 September 2025.

Scheduling Under Uncertainty For Industry 4.0 Applications: A Simulation-Based Genetic Algorithm Approach

Beyza Günesen Akansu¹, Muzaffer Kapanoğlu²

¹ Eskisehir Osmangazi University/Industrial Engineering, Eskisehir, Turkey
beyza.gunesen@ogu.edu.tr

² Eskisehir Osmangazi University/Industrial Engineering, Eskisehir, Turkey
muzaffer@ogu.edu.tr

KEYWORDS – Simheuristic, Simulation, Scheduling, Optimization

ABSTRACT

In highly uncertain and complex environments like industrial production systems, accounting for system variability is essential for informed and resilient decision-making. Industry 4.0 envisions intelligent systems that autonomously make decisions based on comprehensive analyses of current and future states. Incorporating uncertainty into production planning models, rather than relying solely on deterministic assumptions, is key to achieving these goals.

Simulation enables realistic modelling of complex systems with minimal assumptions, making it essential to Industry 4.0 technologies like digital twins. Though effective in capturing stochastic behaviour, simulation struggles to explore large solution spaces efficiently. Combining it with metaheuristics addresses this by leveraging simulation's feedback and uncertainty management with the search power of metaheuristics, leading to more robust and comprehensive solutions.

Most production planning studies rely on deterministic models, often neglecting real-world uncertainties. This study presents a simulation-optimization approach for the single machine scheduling problem with stochastic processing times and sequence-dependent setup times. A genetic Algorithm (GA) solves a simplified deterministic version of the problem in each iteration, generating promising solutions, which are then evaluated through multiple replications in a discrete event simulation. The simulation provides feedback based on the average and variance of fitness values, which is used to update the pool of promising solutions fed back to the GA. After completing all generations, the best solution is simulated over a longer horizon to refine its confidence interval. This process assesses Schedule performance under uncertainty and enhances optimization with realistic feedback. To validate the method, it is tested on problems of varying sizes and compared with the traditional GA+Simulation approach, demonstrating superior scheduling performance.

1 INTRODUCTION

The reflections of changes in consumer behaviour on the market have led to an increased demand for product variety. Consequently, the need to respond rapidly to such demands [1] has compelled manufacturing companies to design their systems accordingly and to structure them in a

way that enables swift adaptation to innovations. The main goal of production planning is to determine production quantities over a specific time horizon by taking into account uncertain conditions such as machine breakdowns, labour shortages, delivery delays, and quality issues [2]. Depending on the company's strategic priorities, the objective may be to implement the most cost-effective, fastest, or highest-quality production plan. However, continuously evolving conditions have a substantial impact on production planning, and the urgency to effectively manage uncertainty and complexity in dynamic environments is increasingly evident [3]. Strategic decisions in production planning typically begin with sales and operations planning (S&OP) or aggregate production planning. At the tactical level, medium-term plans are addressed within the framework of material requirements planning (MRP). At the operational level, production planning encompasses detailed daily or shift-based scheduling along with real-time production control. These hierarchical decision levels differ in terms of planning horizons and the granularity of data, as longer-term planning is typically associated with higher levels of uncertainty [4].

Although many deterministic models have been developed to solve production planning problems, practical planning environments are often subject to uncertainty, which limits the effectiveness of such models [5]. One of the core objectives of Industry 4.0 is to operate production systems in a flexible and competitive manner while simultaneously enhancing their capacity to respond effectively to unpredictable events and dynamic [6-9]. Addressing uncertainty systematically at each level of production planning is not only essential for enhancing the effectiveness of production management but also fundamental for realising the vision of Industry 4.0. In this regard, simulation offers an advantage over analytical techniques, as it does not require extensive simplifying assumptions, enabling more accurate modelling of uncertainty in complex systems [10-11]. This aspect is commonly addressed using approaches such as stochastic programming, fuzzy programming, and dynamic programming. However, these models tend to lack the level of accuracy and detail that simulation-based methods can provide [12]. Additionally, the challenges associated with solving pure mathematical models underscore the value of simulation as a practical tool for handling complex computations.

Simheuristics are methods that integrate simulation within a metaheuristic framework, enabling the consideration of stochastic objective functions and constraints [13]. The integration of simulation models with optimisation techniques facilitates the development of effective decision support tools that combine the strengths of both methodologies. This integrated approach forms the foundation for employing simulation-optimization (SO) methods [14], particularly for complex and stochastic industrial problems such as production scheduling [15]. SO approaches encompass the use of simulation for solution evaluation, analytical model development, and solution generation [12]. They include both exact solution methods such as mathematical programming [16-19], and powerful search techniques such as genetic algorithms [20], simulated annealing [21], and iterative local search [22].

Although simulation-based approaches are among the most powerful tools for modelling complex production systems, simulation runs can become computationally expensive [23],[15]. In the classical SO framework, it is common to allocate a fixed number of simulation replications to each candidate solution at every iteration. However, since candidate solutions may vary in terms of importance and characteristics, this fixed repetition strategy can limit the discovery of higher-quality solutions [24]. The allocation of computational budgets represents a significant challenge in implementing SO and simheuristic methods, yet it has received limited attention in the literature [25].

This study focuses on the single-machine scheduling problem, an operational-level production planning problem, where the goal is to minimise total tardiness. The processing times are stochastic, and the setup times between jobs are sequence-dependent. To effectively address the stochastic nature of the problem—where deterministic solution methods may fall short—a simheuristic approach that combines Genetic Algorithm (GA) with discrete-event simulation is proposed. In the proposed method, the Optimal Computing Budget Allocation (OCBA) procedure is employed to ensure efficient use of simulation resources. The candidate solutions to be evaluated by OCBA are selected by a Random Forest (RF) model, which is trained in each iteration and guides the search in the

solution space. The RF model serves as a learning-based prediction mechanism while also enhancing OCBA's capability to allocate simulation replications more effectively.

- Although the literature extensively studies single-machine scheduling problems, few studies jointly consider stochastic processing times and sequence-dependent setup times. This study contributes to the field by incorporating both sources of uncertainty.
- To reduce simulation effort, efficiently use computational resources, and make learning-based decisions on intermediate solutions, the OCBA mechanism, guided by a Random Forest prediction model, is integrated with the Genetic Algorithm (GA). This framework offers a novel and effective solution approach within simulation-based metaheuristics.
- The study evaluates the quality and reliability of the best-found solution. In this regard, the proposed method analyses solution performance under uncertainty, thereby enhancing its relevance for real-world applications.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

This section reviews the studies focused on single-machine scheduling problems with stochastic processing times. It then discusses simulation-optimization (SO), one of the most commonly adopted methods for generating solutions under uncertainty, followed by an examination of simheuristic approaches integrated with the Optimal Computing Budget Allocation (OCBA) procedure.

Single-machine scheduling problems continue to hold relevance in Industry 4.0 environments [26]. Due to their relatively simple structure, they provide a practical means to decompose complex manufacturing systems into more manageable sub-problems. The literature offers both deterministic [27-29] and stochastic [30] methods for addressing this class of problems. [31] is considered one of the pioneering works incorporating stochastic processing times, proposing a branch-and-bound method to minimise total weighted tardiness. [32], introduced a dynamic scheduling method aimed at minimising the number of tardy jobs. [33], developed a stochastic scheduling model that minimises the total number of early and late jobs. Later, [34] proposed an exact solution algorithm to minimise the expected cost, combining the squared idle time and the weighted squared tardiness, assuming stochastic processing durations.

[35] examined the total weighted tardiness problem with stochastic processing times and incorporated deterioration effects, proposing a hybrid method combining branch-and-bound with simulated annealing. [36], similar to [34], introduced a robust stochastic programming model accounting for idle time. Their bi-objective model simultaneously minimises mean completion time and early/late completion penalties. [37] addressed a risk-averse version of the stochastic scheduling problem by minimising the conditional value-at-risk (CVaR) of total flow time. [38], formulated the problem as a second-order cone mixed-integer programming model to minimise total tardiness. They proposed a novel branch-and-bound algorithm with dominance rules and new bounding strategies.

Despite the growing body of work addressing scheduling problems with stochastic processing times, no existing study was found that applied a simulation-optimization (SO) approach to the single-machine scheduling problem with both stochastic durations and sequence-dependent setup times.

SO approaches have gained considerable attention in recent years as a prominent research area [39]. The digital transformation associated with Industry 4.0 has necessitated the re-evaluation of production planning and scheduling methods, further encouraging the use of SO techniques [40]. For example, [41] presented an SO approach involving a simulation model for production planning and a MILP model for scheduling in a human–robot collaborative assembly line. Simulation results were used to update the MILP parameters iteratively. Similarly, [18] proposed a two-tiered model—master and sub-problems—for flow shop scheduling. The master problem is solved exactly, and inputs are iteratively refined using simulation results from the subproblem.

Other iterative SO approaches include [12] for pulp and paper scheduling, [11] for job shop scheduling, and [42] for sales and operations planning. These studies demonstrate the increasing use of simulation to validate the real-world feasibility of optimisation-generated plans [43]. SO

approaches vary significantly in structure, often tailored to the nature of the specific problem addressed [12].

Simheuristics represent a subclass of SO methods that combine simulation with metaheuristics to solve combinatorial optimisation problems with stochastic elements [13]. The framework was formalised by [44], with applications spanning various domains. Given the current study's focus on scheduling, we examine simheuristics in production planning. [45] proposed a simheuristic based on NSGA-II and Monte Carlo simulation for a stochastic flexible job shop scheduling problem. Their approach minimises total tardiness and tardiness risk simultaneously, relying on simulation to evaluate the stochastic fitness of solutions during search. To reduce computational cost, only new individuals were simulated in each iteration.

[46] addressed the same problem using a similar simheuristic but employed the equilibrium optimizer (EO) for generating initial solutions. [47] developed a simheuristic combining greedy local search with Monte Carlo simulation for a parallel machine scheduling problem with stochastic processing and release times. Their method applies limited simulation replications to all solutions, with more extensive replications allocated to elite solutions to ensure statistical reliability.

[48] proposed a digital twin framework synchronised with real-time data, using GA and simulation to model a flow shop drilling station. Real-world data was used to calculate breakdown probabilities, and simulation outcomes were used to evaluate the schedules. [49] developed a simheuristic using local search and Monte Carlo simulation for stochastic maintenance planning. Simulation was applied to promising candidates during each iteration and to elite solutions in the final iteration.

[44] proposed a simulated annealing-based simheuristic for determining MRP parameters such as lot size, safety stock, and lead times. Their method introduced a Simulation Budget Management (SBM) mechanism to allocate simulation resources wisely. These studies reflect the growing interest in simheuristics for scheduling problems, largely due to the inadequacy of deterministic methods in uncertain environments and the ability of simulation to represent system dynamics more accurately.

The literature reveals various strategies for optimising limited simulation budgets. Some studies simulate only superior solutions at each iteration and all elite solutions in the final round [45],[49], while others stop simulations once statistical confidence intervals are achieved [50],[47]. Analytical methods such as OCBA [51],[25] and SBM [33] analyse statistical properties like variance and mean to allocate simulation replications optimally.

The reviewed literature highlights the growing use of SO approaches to support both the realisation of Industry 4.0 goals and the analysis of complex production systems. The design of SO methods often includes problem-specific mechanisms to reduce simulation costs. Simheuristics, as SO methods tailored to combinatorial problems, enable simulation-guided solution exploration. Efficient simulation budget management is frequently emphasised as a critical factor in the simheuristics literature.

This study proposes a novel simheuristic approach that combines simulation filtering guided by a Random Forest model with the OCBA procedure to allocate simulation replications efficiently.

3 PROPOSED METHOD

The proposed learning-based simheuristic approach consists of three main components: a metaheuristic algorithm, a surrogate model, and a simulation model. The overall architecture of the proposed method and the interrelationships between its components are illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Architecture of proposed simheuristic

3.1 Genetic Algorithm

In the proposed approach, a classical Genetic Algorithm (GA) is employed as the metaheuristic component to explore the solution space effectively. Chromosomes are represented using a permutation-based encoding scheme, which is commonly applied in sequencing problems. The selection of parent solutions is carried out using the tournament selection method, known for its simplicity and efficiency. For crossover, the Order Crossover (OX) operator is utilized, where segments from two parents are combined while preserving the relative order of remaining genes. Mutation is performed by randomly removing a gene from its position and reinserting it into another randomly selected location within the chromosome. This configuration enables the GA to balance exploration and exploitation, supporting the generation of high-quality solutions.

3.2 Simulation

In classical simheuristic approaches, the simulation component addresses uncertainties in the model and provides feedback to the metaheuristic component, thereby contributing to a more effective guidance of the search process [13]. In the simheuristic framework proposed in this study, however, simulation results provide feedback not only to the metaheuristic component but also to the prediction model. As a result, the prediction model is retrained in each iteration using newly obtained data, aiming to improve its performance and enhance the accuracy of search guidance. Moreover, the stochastic fitness values obtained from the simulation are directly used in updating the elite solution list, thus adding a layer of reliability to the decision-making process under uncertainty. In the simulation, the processing times of each job are generated according to a normal distribution based on predefined mean and standard deviation values. The stochastic counterpart of the fitness value, which represents total tardiness, is computed through simulation using these random variables.

3.3 Optimal Computing Budget Allocation

The simulation model represents the stochastic behaviour of the system and is responsible for evaluating its performance under uncertainty. To statistically justify the model's stochastic behaviour, the number of simulation replications is of critical importance. According to the Law of Large Numbers, as the sample size increases, the estimates obtained from the sample converge to the true values [51]. However, this process results in significant consumption of simulation resources. To manage simulation budget usage efficiently in this study, the Optimal Computing Budget Allocation (OCBA) procedure, originally proposed by [52], is employed. The objective of the OCBA procedure is to allocate the simulation budget among candidate solutions in a way that maximises the probability of correctly identifying the best-performing solution.

3.4 Random Forest

The Random Forest (RF) method, originally proposed by [53], is a machine learning technique based on an ensemble structure composed of decision trees. It inherently incorporates feature selection and variable interactions into the learning process. RF models are capable of effectively handling discrete representations and are known for producing robust and reliable results, even when trained on high-dimensional data with limited sample sizes [54].

RF trees can be constructed either as classification or regression trees (CART). Classification trees are designed for cases where the dependent variable consists of a finite number of unordered categorical values, and their prediction error is typically measured using misclassification cost. In contrast, regression trees are used when the dependent variable is continuous or consists of ordered discrete values, and the prediction error is usually computed as the squared difference between observed and predicted values [55]. In RF models using regression trees, each individual tree serves as a weak predictor. These trees are trained on different subsets of the data using randomly selected features. During prediction, the final output is obtained by averaging the predictions from all individual trees. The randomisation mechanism in RF helps reduce the risk of overfitting.

In the problem addressed in this study, each solution candidate is represented by a chromosome, i.e., a permutation vector. RF models are particularly well-suited for processing such discrete and ordered structures, and are therefore selected for use in the prediction phase due to their effectiveness in learning from permutation-based inputs and their relatively low risk of overfitting. A graphical representation of the prediction flow in the RF technique is provided in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Random Forest graphical representation [56]

The primary motivation for integrating the surrogate model into the proposed approach is to enable the efficient use of simulation resources. By intelligently selecting the candidate solutions to be evaluated via simulation, the goal is to enhance both the quality and the reliability of the solutions.

In the developed simheuristic, each individual in the randomly generated initial population is evaluated using a fixed number of simulation replications, and their total tardiness values are recorded. These simulation outputs are then used to train a Random Forest (RF) regression model, which will be employed in later generations to estimate the stochastic fitness values of new individuals. Accordingly, both the characteristic features of each individual and their corresponding simulation-based tardiness values are transferred to the model, initiating the learning process. The characteristic features used to train the RF model are as follows:

- Total Setup Time: The sum of the setup times required for transitions between consecutive jobs.
- Standard Deviation of Setup Times: Indicates the variability of setup durations, allowing the model to learn how unbalanced sequences affect total tardiness.
- Indices of the First and Last Jobs: Identify the initial and final jobs in the sequence. This feature captures the impact of starting or ending with critical jobs.
- Average Due Date of the First Few Jobs: Helps the model detect the presence of early-due jobs that should be prioritised.
- Number of Critical Transitions: Represents the number of setup times that exceed the 75th percentile, highlighting transitions with unusually high setup durations.

In subsequent generations, the RF model is used to estimate the stochastic fitness values of the newly evolved individuals. Individuals whose predicted fitness values fall below a predefined threshold are transferred to the candidate list, and simulation replications are allocated only to those individuals. Within the developed algorithm, the RF model serves as a bridge between the deterministic and stochastic components, guiding the simulation effort towards the most promising solutions.

4 COMPUTATIONAL RESULTS

The prediction-oriented simheuristic algorithm was implemented in Python 3.9, and all test instance results were obtained on a computer equipped with an Intel(R) Core(TM) i5-1135G7 @ 2.40GHz 2.42GHz processor and 8.00 GB RAM. The performance of the proposed GA+RF+OCBA_Sim algorithm was evaluated in comparison with both the classical (deterministic)

GA and the GA+OCBA_Sim approach. To enable a fair comparison, 100 simulation replications were applied to the best solution obtained by the classical GA, and the results were evaluated based on the average performance. The comparison with the classical GA aims to emphasize the importance of considering the stochastic nature of the problem.

The comparative analysis between GA+OCBA_Sim and GA+RF+OCBA_Sim is conducted to assess the contribution of the integrated RF model to the simheuristic framework. Section 4.1 provides details on the generation of test instances, while Section 4.2 presents the computational results and comparative analyses.

4.1 Generation of Test Instances

For the single-machine scheduling problem with sequence-dependent setup times and stochastic processing durations, test instances were generated based on the procedure proposed by [36]. Processing times follow a normal distribution $N(\mu_i, \sigma_i)$, where μ_i is the mean and σ_i is the standard deviation. The mean processing times μ_i are randomly drawn from a uniform distribution $U(10,20)$.

Although the original problem formulation in [36] does not include sequence-dependent setup times, in this study, setup times were introduced and generated using the same uniform distribution $U(10,20)$, consistent with the distribution used for the processing time means. The standard deviations σ_i of the processing times were drawn from a uniform distribution $U(0.5 * \mu_i, 1.5 * \mu_i)$. Due dates were generated from a uniform distribution $U(0.6 * \sum_i(\mu_i + \bar{s}_i), 1.4 * \sum_i(\mu_i + \bar{s}_i))$, where \bar{s} denotes the average sequence-dependent setup time. In the deterministic phase of the proposed approach, the mean values μ_i of the processing times were used.

Table 1 Performance Results for the 50-Job Test Instances

Nu	GA				GA+OCBA Simulation				GA+RF+OCBA Simulation			
	MIN	RD	AVG	ARD	MIN	RD	AVG	ARD	MIN	RD	AVG	ARD
1	1818	1.55	1947.5	1.69	2527.6	0.94	2921.5	0.36	3496.1	0.00	4844.6	0.03
2	1629	1.83	1795.6	1.45	2188.4	1.24	2551.3	0.38	2463.0	0.00	3142.2	0.09
3	2086	1.58	2333.4	1.53	2938.5	1.00	3203.5	0.30	3674.0	0.07	4255.7	0.05
4	1846	1.64	1995.8	1.56	2625.4	0.33	2780.9	0.38	2938.0	0.00	3954.7	0.05
5	2294	1.48	2491.9	1.65	3028.4	0.17	3435.1	0.28	3418.1	0.39	4319.8	0.05
6	1604	1.94	1714.5	1.79	2398.7	0.68	2950.2	0.33	2980.4	0.32	4024.5	0.03
7	2710	1.48	2841.2	1.48	3276.6	0.53	3800.5	0.15	3820.8	0.00	4234.9	0.13
8	2095	1.77	2277.9	1.45	2970.6	0.00	3167.5	0.35	3599.2	0.00	4490.9	0.03
9	3243	2.01	3429.7	1.62	4181.7	1.36	4587.6	0.35	4292.4	0.18	5077.9	0.03
10	1347	1.47	1508.6	1.37	2017.8	0.00	2222.5	0.12	2490.3	0.00	2900.4	0.04

4.2 Results

In this section, the results of the test problems with 50 jobs are presented. Each problem instance was executed 10 times using the classical GA, GA+OCBA_Sim, and GA+RF+OCBA_Sim methods. The summary of the results is provided in Table 1. To ensure a more robust evaluation of solution quality, the best solution obtained in each run was subjected to 100 independent simulation replications. Based on these simulations, the mean and sample standard deviation of the resulting total tardiness values were calculated, and a 95% confidence interval was constructed. To compute the confidence interval, the error margin was derived using the t-distribution, and lower and upper bounds of the interval were established accordingly. This allowed for assessing whether the obtained solutions fall within the corresponding confidence intervals. In Table 1, the MIN column indicates the minimum total tardiness obtained across 10 runs, while the AVG column shows the average total tardiness. The RD (Relative Distance) column represents the relative distance of the minimum solution from the corresponding confidence interval. The ARD column reports the average of RD values over all runs. If the minimum solution lies within the

confidence interval, RD is assigned a value of 0; otherwise, it is calculated using the formula provided below.

$$Relative\ Distance\ (RD) = \frac{Solution - Confidence\ Interval\ Bound}{CI\ Upper\ Bound - CI\ Lower\ Bound} \tag{1}$$

Figure 3: Graph of minimum tardiness for 50-job test problems

Figure 4: Plot of Relative Distance for 50-job test problems

Figures 3 and 4 present graphical representations of the results for the test instances with 50 jobs. Figure 3 illustrates the trend of minimum total tardiness values obtained from 10 runs across 10 different problems for each of the three methods. Figure 4 illustrates box plots of the average relative distances (RD) computed over the 10 runs. Although the proposed method generally yielded higher minimum tardiness values compared to the other two methods, its solutions appear to be more reliable in terms of consistency. This conclusion is supported by the box plots, which indicate that the proposed method produced solutions with lower variability and better stability under uncertainty.

5 CONCLUSION

In this study, a simulation-optimization (SO) approach has been developed to solve the single-machine scheduling problem with stochastic processing times and sequence-dependent setup times. In stochastic problems, simheuristics—hybrid methods in which the deterministic version of the problem is first solved using a metaheuristic, and then the resulting solutions are evaluated through simulation incorporating stochastic parameters—have gained attention in the literature [13]. To reduce simulation costs, various methods have been proposed. In this study, the Optimal Computing Budget Allocation (OCBA) procedure was adopted to make efficient use of limited simulation resources. OCBA focuses on promising solutions likely to enter the elite list and assigns more simulation replications to those candidates, thereby improving the efficiency of simulation usage.

To further support the economical allocation of simulation effort and to enhance prediction accuracy, a machine learning-based prediction model was integrated into the simheuristic framework. In the proposed method, deterministic solutions are generated using a Genetic Algorithm (GA), while the selection of individuals for the candidate list is guided by a Random Forest (RF) model. The RF model estimates the stochastic fitness values of all individuals in the population, and those with predicted fitness values below a predefined threshold are transferred to the candidate list. Simulation replications are then allocated to these candidates in accordance with the OCBA procedure, improving the overall computational efficiency.

The RF model is incrementally updated from generation to generation using both the initial population and the candidate individuals evaluated in each generation, thus enhancing its prediction accuracy over time. This architecture forms a simulation-optimization framework that effectively integrates deterministic and stochastic components, balancing solution quality with computational efficiency.

To evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed approach, classical GA and GA+OCBA_Sim methods were used as benchmarks. The classical GA method offers a baseline that ignores the stochastic nature of the problem, while GA+OCBA_Sim represents the proposed framework without the predictive support of the RF model. This comparative setup allows for isolating and quantifying the contribution of the RF model to overall solution quality.

Test instances of varying sizes were generated, and results were reported for problems with 50 jobs. Although the proposed simheuristic did not always yield the lowest total tardiness values, it consistently produced more reliable solutions. Specifically, in test problems with processing time variances drawn from $U(0.5 * \mu_i, 1.5 * \mu_i)$, the relative distance (RD) analyses demonstrated that solutions generated by the proposed method had a higher likelihood of falling within the confidence interval and exhibited lower variability. These results highlight the strength of the proposed approach in producing more predictable and robust solutions for production planning problems under uncertainty.

In future work, further analyses will be conducted on problems of varying sizes and with different levels of variance to explore the improvement potential of the proposed approach. In addition, the adaptability of the prediction-oriented simheuristic to other scheduling and production planning problems will be investigated to assess its generalizability and broaden its application scope.

REFERENCES

- [1] O. E. Oluyisola, S. Bhalla, F. Sgarbossa, and J. O. Strandhagen, "Designing and developing smart production planning and control systems in the industry 4.0 era: a methodology and case study," *Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing*, vol. 33, no. 1, pp. 311-332, 2022.
- [2] M. Schmidt and T. Schäfers, "Integrated production planning and control of cyber-physical production systems," in *Progress in Cyber-Physical Systems*, Cham: Springer, 2017, pp. 203–215.
- [3] R. Busert and A. Fay, "Flexible control systems in cyber-physical production systems," in *Proc. 23rd Int. Conf. Emerging Technologies and Factory Automation (ETFA)*, 2018, pp. 1–8.

- [4] H. Ganterer, M. Schramm, and M. Seifert, "Hierarchical production planning in global manufacturing networks," *Int. J. Prod. Res.*, vol. 52, no. 17, pp. 5143–5161, 2014.
- [5] X. Zhang, M. Prajapati, and E. Peden, "A stochastic production planning model under uncertain seasonal demand and market growth," *Int. J. Prod. Res.*, vol. 49, no. 7, pp. 1957–1975, 2011.
- [6] D. A. Rossit, F. Tohmé, and M. Frutos, "Industry 4.0: Smart scheduling," *Int. J. Prod. Res.*, vol. 57, no. 12, pp. 3802–3813, 2018.
- [7] C. G. Machado, M. P. Winroth, and E. H. D. Ribeiro da Silva, "Sustainable manufacturing in Industry 4.0: An emerging research agenda," *Int. J. Prod. Res.*, vol. 58, no. 5, pp. 1462–1484, 2020.
- [8] F. Rosin, P. Forget, S. Lamouri, and R. Pellerin, "Impacts of Industry 4.0 technologies on lean principles," *Int. J. Prod. Res.*, vol. 58, no. 6, pp. 1644–1661, 2020.
- [9] X. Liu, F. Chu, F. Zheng, C. Chu, and M. Liu, "Parallel machine scheduling with stochastic release times and processing times," *Int. J. Prod. Res.*, vol. 59, no. 20, pp. 6327–6346, 2021.
- [10] K. J. Glowacka, R. M. Henry, and J. H. May, "A hybrid data mining/simulation approach for modelling outpatient no-shows in clinic scheduling," *J. Oper. Res. Soc.*, vol. 60, no. 8, pp. 1056–1068, 2009.
- [11] K. Kulkarni and J. Venkateswaran, "Iterative simulation and optimization approach for job shop scheduling," in *Proc. Winter Simulation Conf.*, 2014.
- [12] G. Figueira and B. Almada-Lobo, "Hybrid simulation–optimization methods: A taxonomy and discussion," *Simul. Model. Pract. Theory*, vol. 46, pp. 118–134, 2014.
- [13] A. A. Juan, J. Faulin, S. E. Grasman, M. Rabe, and G. Figueira, "A review of simheuristics: Extending metaheuristics to deal with stochastic combinatorial optimization problems," *Oper. Res. Perspect.*, vol. 2, pp. 62–72, 2015.
- [14] A. April, F. Glover, and M. Laguna, "Practical introduction to simulation optimization," in *Proc. Winter Simulation Conf.*, vol. 1, pp. 71–78, 2003.
- [15] E. Nejati, E. Ghaedy-Heidary, A. Ghasemi, and S. A. Torabi, "A machine learning-based simulation metamodeling method for dynamic scheduling in smart manufacturing systems," *Comput. Ind. Eng.*, vol. 196, p. 110507, 2024.
- [16] A. Matta, "Simulation optimization with mathematical programming representation of discrete event systems," in *Proc. Winter Simulation Conf.*, 2008, pp. 1393–1400, doi: 10.1109/WSC.2008.4736215.
- [17] M. Zhang, A. Matta, et al., "A simulation-based Benders' cuts generation for the joint workstation, workload and buffer allocation problem," in *Proc. 13th IEEE Conf. Autom. Sci. Eng. (CASE)*, 2017, pp. 1067–1072.
- [18] R. Wallrath and M. B. Franke, "Integration of MILP and discrete-event simulation for flow shop scheduling using Benders cuts," *Comput. Chem. Eng.*, vol. 189, p. 108809, 2024.
- [19] J. Y. Bang and Y. D. Kim, "Hierarchical production planning for semiconductor wafer fabrication based on linear programming and discrete-event simulation," *IEEE Trans. Autom. Sci. Eng.*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 326–336, 2009.
- [20] E. Ghazavi and M. M. Lotfi, "Formulation of customers' shopping path in shelf space planning: A simulation-optimization approach," *Expert Syst. Appl.*, vol. 55, pp. 243–254, 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.eswa.2016.01.043.
- [21] A. Hatami-Marbini, S. M. Sajadi, and H. Malekpour, "Optimal control and simulation for production planning of network failure-prone manufacturing systems with perishable goods," *Comput. Ind. Eng.*, vol. 146, p. 106614, 2020.

- [22] A. Gr̄asas, A. A. Juan, and H. R. Lourenço, "SimILS: a simulation-based extension of the iterated local search metaheuristic for stochastic combinatorial optimization," *J. Simul.*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 69–77, 2016.
- [23] L. H. Lee, N. A. Pujowidianto, L. W. Li, C. H. Chen, and C. M. Yap, "Approximate simulation budget allocation for selecting the best design in the presence of stochastic constraints," *IEEE Trans. Autom. Control*, vol. 57, no. 11, pp. 2940–2945, 2012.
- [24] G. Kou, H. Xiao, M. Cao, and L. H. Lee, "Optimal computing budget allocation for the vector evaluated genetic algorithm in multi-objective simulation optimization," *Automatica*, vol. 129, p. 109599, 2021.
- [25] Y. Clapper, J. Berkhout, and R. Bekker, "Adaptive budget allocation in simheuristics applied to stochastic home healthcare routing and scheduling," *Comput. Ind. Eng.*, vol. 198, p. 110651, 2024.
- [26] R. Martinelli, F. C. M. Q. Mariano, and C. B. Martins, "Single machine scheduling in make to order environments: A systematic review," *Comput. Ind. Eng.*, vol. 169, p. 108190, 2022.
- [27] M. Feldmann and D. Biskup, "Single-machine scheduling for minimizing earliness and tardiness penalties by meta-heuristic approaches," *Comput. Ind. Eng.*, vol. 44, no. 2, pp. 307–323, 2003.
- [28] S. Tanaka, S. Fujikuma, and M. Araki, "An exact algorithm for single-machine scheduling without machine idle time," *J. Scheduling*, vol. 12, pp. 575–593, 2009.
- [29] A. B. Keha, K. Khowala, and J. W. Fowler, "Mixed integer programming formulations for single machine scheduling problems," *Comput. Ind. Eng.*, vol. 56, no. 1, pp. 357–367, 2009.
- [30] C. C. Lu, S. W. Lin, and K. C. Ying, "Robust scheduling on a single machine to minimize total flow time," *Comput. Oper. Res.*, vol. 39, no. 7, pp. 1682–1691, 2012.
- [31] W. J. Gutjahr, A. Hellmayr, and G. C. Pflug, "Optimal stochastic single-machine-tardiness scheduling by stochastic branch-and-bound," *Eur. J. Oper. Res.*, vol. 117, no. 2, pp. 396–413, 1999.
- [32] W. Jang, "Dynamic scheduling of stochastic jobs on a single machine," *Eur. J. Oper. Res.*, vol. 138, no. 3, pp. 518–530, 2002.
- [33] H. M. Soroush, "Minimizing the weighted number of early and tardy jobs in a stochastic single machine scheduling problem," *Eur. J. Oper. Res.*, vol. 181, no. 1, pp. 266–287, 2007.
- [34] H. M. Soroush, "Solving a stochastic single machine problem with initial idle time and quadratic objective," *Comput. Oper. Res.*, vol. 37, no. 7, pp. 1328–1347, 2010.
- [35] M. M. Mazdeh, H. Haddadm, and P. Ghanbari, "Solving a single machine stochastic scheduling problem using a branch and bound algorithm and simulated annealing," *Int. J. Manag. Sci. Eng. Manag.*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 110–118, 2012.
- [36] A. Salmasnia, M. Khatami, R. B. Kazemzadeh, and S. H. Zegordi, "Bi-objective single machine scheduling problem with stochastic processing times," *Top*, vol. 23, pp. 275–297, 2015.
- [37] Z. Chang, S. Song, Y. Zhang, J. Y. Ding, R. Zhang, and R. Chiong, "Distributionally robust single machine scheduling with risk aversion," *Eur. J. Oper. Res.*, vol. 256, no. 1, pp. 261–274, 2017.
- [38] S. Niu, S. Song, J. Y. Ding, Y. Zhang, and R. Chiong, "Distributionally robust single machine scheduling with the total tardiness criterion," *Comput. Oper. Res.*, vol. 101, pp. 13–28, 2019.
- [39] S. Amaran, N. V. Sahinidis, B. Sharda, and S. J. Bury, "Simulation optimization: a review of algorithms and applications," *Ann. Oper. Res.*, vol. 240, pp. 351–380, 2016.

- [40] C. Chen, T. L. Kong, and W. Kan, "Identifying the promising production planning and scheduling method for manufacturing in Industry 4.0: a literature review," *Prod. Manuf. Res.*, vol. 11, no. 1, p. 2279329, 2023.
- [41] M. Vieira, S. Moniz, B. S. Gonçalves, T. Pinto-Varela, A. P. Barbosa-Póvoa, and P. Neto, "A two-level optimisation-simulation method for production planning and scheduling: the industrial case of a human–robot collaborative assembly line," *Int. J. Prod. Res.*, vol. 60, no. 9, pp. 2942–2962, 2022.
- [42] L. L. Lim, G. Alpan, and B. Penz, "A simulation-optimization approach for sales and operations planning in build-to-order industries with distant sourcing: Focus on the automotive industry," *Comput. Ind. Eng.*, vol. 112, pp. 469–482, 2017.
- [43] D. Luo, S. Thevenin, and A. Dolgui, "A state-of-the-art on production planning in Industry 4.0," *Int. J. Prod. Res.*, vol. 61, no. 19, pp. 6602–6632, 2023.
- [44] W. Seiringer, J. Castaneda, K. Altendorfer, J. Panadero, and A. A. Juan, "Applying simheuristics to minimize overall costs of an MRP planned production system," *Algorithms*, vol. 15, no. 2, p. 40, 2022.
- [45] C. A. Rodríguez-Espinosa, E. M. González-Neira, and G. M. Zambrano-Rey, "A simheuristic approach using the NSGA-II to solve a bi-objective stochastic flexible job shop problem," *J. Simul.*, vol. 18, no. 4, pp. 646–670, 2024.
- [46] S. Nessari, R. Tavakkoli-Moghaddam, H. Bakhshi-Khaniki, and A. Bozorgi-Amiri, "A hybrid simheuristic algorithm for solving bi-objective stochastic flexible job shop scheduling problems," *Decis. Anal. J.*, vol. 11, p. 100485, 2024.
- [47] Abu-Marrul, R. Martinelli, S. Hamacher, and I. Gribkovskaia, "Simheuristic algorithm for a stochastic parallel machine scheduling problem with periodic re-planning assessment," *Ann. Oper. Res.*, vol. 320, no. 2, pp. 547–572, 2023.
- [48] E. Negri, L. Fumagalli, and M. Macchi, "A review of digital twin applications in manufacturing," *Comput. Ind.*, vol. 126, p. 103362, 2021.
- [49] D. G. Coelho, M. J. Souza, and L. P. Cota, "A simheuristic-based algorithm for the stochastic long-term maintenance scheduling problem," *Comput. Ind. Eng.*, vol. 177, p. 108983, 2023.
- [50] M. Rabe, M. Deininger, and A. A. Juan, "Speeding up computational times in simheuristics combining genetic algorithms with discrete-event simulation," *Simul. Model. Pract. Theory*, vol. 103, p. 102089, 2020.
- [51] J. T. Lin, C. C. Chiu, and Y. H. Chang, "Simulation-based optimization approach for simultaneous scheduling of vehicles and machines with processing time uncertainty in FMS," *Flex. Serv. Manuf. J.*, vol. 31, pp. 104–141, 2019.
- [52] C. H. Chen and L. H. Lee, *Stochastic Simulation Optimization: An Optimal Computing Budget Allocation*, vol. 1. Singapore: World Scientific, 2011.
- [53] L. Breiman, "Random forests," *Machine Learning*, vol. 45, pp. 5–32, 2001.
- [54] Y. Qi, "Random forest for bioinformatics," in *Ensemble Machine Learning*, C. Zhang and Y. Ma, Eds. Boston, MA: Springer, 2012, pp. 307–323.
- [55] W. Y. Loh, "Classification and regression trees," *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 14–23, 2011.
- [56] T. Ikeguchi, S. Sudo, Y. Koguma, and M. Nakata, "A Random Forest-Assisted Local Search for Expensive Permutation-based Combinatorial Optimization Problems," in *Proc. 2024 IEEE Congress on Evolutionary Computation (CEC)*, 2024, pp. 01–08.